

QUIZ**LAST NAME: ORTUOSTE****FIRST NAME: RAIZAH****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did not use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Why is creating a Writing “Source Bank” essential for writers?**
 - It helps the writer find writing ideas that is well documented while being able to explore the community around him. ¹**
 - It supports writers in remembering their source of information which is vital for the bibliography.
 - It provides the writer’s source of funding during publication.
 - It is not essential but can be a big help during pre-publication.
2. **All are examples of Creative Writing except:**
 - Myths.

¹ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. (Burlington, Wisconsin, 1990), 47.

- Anecdotes.
- Diaries.**²
- Poems.

3. **WHO uses different writing styles, depending on which region a paper is published?**

- Yes, because it will adopt to a specific context allowing respect.
- Yes, but it has two kinds of writing styles.
- No, WHO has no standard rule of style.
- No, WHO uses only one rule of style.**³

4. **In the WHO rule of style, the use of characteristics must be in gender-neutral terms except.**

- Disability status.
- Marital Status.**⁴
- Cultural Background.
- Age.

5. **When do you say that a source is reliable?**

² Ibid, 51.

³ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 1.

⁴ Ibid, 55.

- If the source is a website, its author engages on heated advocacies, attacks other researchers, and makes wild claims.
- When a peer does not review the source.
- When the source is published by a reputable press, author and has notes and bibliography.**⁵
- If the source is seldom cited by other researchers.

6. **What are the common errors in research papers?**

- Grammar, spelling, and inaccurate words.**⁶
- Grammar, sequence of paragraphs, and numbering.
- Grammar, inaccurate bibliography, and inappropriate citations.
- Grammar, spelling, and incorrect usage of punctuation marks.

7. **Use of the WHO abbreviation is allowed when:**

- It is only allowed externally because it shortens the reading time.
- It is never allowed internal or external as it imposes confusion between readers.
- It can be abbreviated when used only with its member states.
- It is used internally in the World Health Organization as everyone is already oriented of its abbreviation.**⁷

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 42.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 6.

⁷ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 3.

8. **What is the most distinct difference of the WHO rule of style from the others?**
- WHO rule of style prefers to run words together than use hyphens.⁸**
 - WHO rule of style prefers to use abbreviations all the time.
 - WHO rule of style has no difference from other rules of style.
 - WHO rule of style of style has a distinct list of abbreviations.
9. **When writing medical terms, WHO rule of style prefers to write in:**
- North American English.
 - British English.⁹**
 - Modern English.
 - Australian English.
10. **Intelligently using sensitive geographical designations is crucial to the WHO rule of style because?**

⁸ Ibid, 14.

⁹ Ibid, 13.

- All WHO publications carry a standard disclaimer on the designation of countries, territories, cities and areas and their authorities and the delamination of frontiers to respect all designations and regions.**¹⁰
- WHO is a governing body which all the states and regions are under the organization.
- WHO publications do not use discriminatory languages due only to its cultural sensitivity.
- WHO publishes critical documents that may hamper the health population.

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¹⁰ Ibid, 6-7.

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